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CDKN inactivation is a major resistance mechanism in cancer.

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We studied whole transcription in resistance associated with specific cancer types, like TNBC, and resistance associated with specific treatments of chemotherapies, like platinum agents and trastuzumab to discover genes and pathways that function to support resistance in human cancer. We identified inactivation of cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor *CDKN* family gene expression as a recurrent transcriptional end product in resistance across settings: resistance to cisplatin in lung cancer cells *in vitro*, resistance to trastuzumab *in vivo* and *in vitro* in HER2+ breast cancer, resistance to the chemotherapy doxorubicin, and resistance that occurs in humans with triple negative breast cancer *in vivo*.